

A multicellular analysis calcium imaging toolbox for ImageJ

“Naturally due to transparency and to adhere to publication guidelines, (it was important to make our data publicly available.) However, we also believe for tool development, and in particular a software tool, data transparency is important to streamline the ability of future users to adopt and implement the resource.”

--- Eric Horstick, West Virginia University

Researcher(s) or Team: Eric Horstick

Dataset(s) used:

<https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/f675cbz84s/1>

Related publication(s):

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Summary

For this study, we developed an open-source software to analyze neural activity using fluorescent reporters. We validated this software using previously published data from our lab and new experiments in zebrafish. In addition, we added analysis from collaborator datasets in *Drosophila* and mouse. The dataset we uploaded to Mendeley is composed of the raw imaging data we acquired to test and validate the efficacy of our software as well as the dataset we used to train an AI model that is integrated into our software for cell segmentation. This also includes a copy of the source code for the software version that is associated with the final accepted publication.

Sharing Methodology

Providing the data is a necessity for publishing with federal funds. However, for my lab it has always been an important goal. For the current manuscript, sharing data and supporting code is particularly important because the development of software intended to be broadly used in the scientific community requires potential users to see how this resource works. In our opinion, providing the validation data and source code is necessary to provide potential users with examples to implement the tool and see how the tool will handle their data during analysis. A generalist repository provided an easy-to-use interface that was also free to use with the quantity of data generated in the study. Data submission into Mendeley Data is a straightforward process. For example, for numerical data we have included this using excel files where each tab represents a figure panel in the associated manuscript.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/cell-reports-methods>

We also used GitHub as this is a standard for source code sharing and comment. For data/source code storage and sharing, I have used GitHub. I believe GitHub is generally easy to use for sharing simple source code as well as documentation for how to use the source code for new application or library development, however it is not reasonable for sharing large files or other types of data files that academic researchers typically produce. I have also shared large data sets, such as genomic sequencing data, using Globus. Although Globus is convenient for transfer, it does not provide storage options. Last, onsite university resources are rapidly getting implemented and evolving to support the growing requirements for data sharing associated with federal funding stipulations. Iterations of these resources are generally increasing ease of use and trying to balance cost effectiveness, which is important for resources supported by grant funds.

Impact

Within neuroscience, using software to measure brain activity has become a standard experiment. However, this software provides an open source, user friendly interface, and visual outputs for each analytic step. This collectively provides a resource that avoids hurdles associated with proprietary software or needing extensive coding knowledge to use. Outside of neuroscience, this software provides an open-source concept for a user interface that easily analyzes imaging data, which can be used in a variety of different formats. This will influence academic software developers to develop new applications for research in a manner that is targeted towards what the average biological researcher understands about the software development process.

Reuse Possibilities

Because this is software, future research will focus on integrating this application into their labs and protocols. Since this is also open source, the current code could serve as a foundation to which additional functions can be added, which would expand the applications.

Thoughts on Sharing and Reuse

In the past few years there have been new requirements for increased, upfront, data transparency. Ultimately, this is a good idea. However, without standardizing the structure and manner that data is shared, there is a significant hurdle in interpreting and using such data. Nevertheless, providing manageable and applicable standards for the diverse types of data generated is nearly impossible. In many cases, the best advice is to work with researchers regarding their data to support efficient usage, interpretation, and reproducibility.

For initial interactions, well documented public data can be a first pass resource for a potential collaborator or interested researcher.

For datasets connected to published manuscripts some direct connection to the manuscript or specific figures represented by subsets of the data should help interpretation and usage.

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Article

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